

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

How does job stress affect job satisfaction and Turnover Intention in Public Hospital, Gianyar, Bali?

Ni Made Dwi Puspitawati *, I Komang Oka Permadi and Adhi Krisna Yuliawan

Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Mahasaraswati Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 21(03), 1105–1114

Publication history: Received on 02 February 2024; revised on 10 March 2024; accepted on 12 March 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.3.0844>

Abstract

The desire to change jobs among hospital nurses is a critical issue related to service quality. Nurses have the desire to move if they feel work stress and the level of job satisfaction tends to decrease. Nurses' high stress levels will cause them to feel less satisfied with their work which will ultimately lead to their intention to leave the hospital. This research aims to (1) analyze the influence of job stress on turnover intention, (2) analyze the influence of job stress on job satisfaction, and (3) analyze the influence of job satisfaction on turnover intention. The sample in this study used a proportional sampling technique which was only aimed at nurses in four divisions, totaling 100 people. The data analysis technique uses SEM-PLS.

The research results show that (1) work stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention, (2) work stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction, and (3) job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. This research implies that a low level of stress at work will increase job satisfaction and reduce their intention to leave the hospital, especially as nurses know the consequences of their work.

Keywords: Job Stress; Job Satisfaction; Turnover Intention; Hospital

1. Introduction

The level of work stress and job satisfaction of nurses in hospitals are key factors that influence the quality of service and patient safety. In complex healthcare environments, nurses play a critical role in providing effective and empathetic care. Therefore, understanding the factors that influence nurses' job satisfaction is very important for hospital management to improve service quality and minimize turnover.

Nurses have the intention to leave the hospital due to discomfort at work. The work stress experienced by nurses can also make nurses dissatisfied with their work and is also the reason why they want to move. Job stress has a positive and significant influence on turnover intention [1][2][3], this shows that higher work stress can increase the turnover intention of the nurse.

Job stress will affect the level of job satisfaction of nurses which ultimately leads to the intention and decision to leave work. Research conducted [4] states that work stress has a negative and significant effect on nurses' job satisfaction, this means that the lower the work stress, the higher the nurses' job satisfaction. Other research conducted by [5] [6], also shows that Job stress has a negative and significant effect on nurses' job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction is also a factor that can influence the level of turnover intention. Job satisfaction will occur if the individual's needs are met, this is related to the degree of liking or disliking associated with nurses, which is an attitude commonly shown by nurses because it is closely related to the rewards, they believe they will get after they do a job. Research conducted by [7][8] states that job satisfaction has a negative effect on turnover intention, which shows that

* Corresponding author: Ni Made Dwi Puspitawati, Email: dwipuspitawati10@unmas.ac.id

job satisfaction with organizational policies and strategies, satisfaction with career development, and satisfaction with supervision, other research conducted by [9][10][11] also shows that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on nurses' turnover intention.

One way that companies can prevent the emergence of turnover intention behavior caused by work stress is to pay attention to nurses' job satisfaction. Perceived job satisfaction can encourage nurses to do their jobs better and encourage nurses to stay with the company. Management needs to reduce the level of turnover intention by paying attention to the level of work stress and job satisfaction with the efforts that the company can make to be able to control problems with turnover intention.

Based on the results of interviews conducted, several nurses stated that they were stressed at work and had a tendency to decrease job satisfaction [12]. This is due to excessive workload, stress, and imbalance of job demands with available resources [13]. Job satisfaction felt by nurses indicates that there is a feeling of dissatisfaction with the work of nurses which is indicated by incentives that are inappropriate or insufficient because nurses feel that their salary does not reflect the value of their work or responsibilities [14]. Based on the results of previous research and the phenomena that occur, researchers are interested in researching the influence of work stress on job satisfaction and nurse turnover intention.

2. Literature Review and Research Hypothesis

2.1. Theory of Planned Behavior

Research conducted by [15] states that a person's behavior depends on the desire to behave (behavioral intention) which consists of three components, namely: attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. The attitude and subjective norm variables are in the "Theory of Reasoned Action", while the third variable appears in the "Theory of Planned Behavior". According to [16] A person's intention to behave can be predicted by three things, namely the attitude towards the behavior which is the overall evaluation of a person regarding the positive or negative aspects of displaying a certain behavior, then the subjective norm [17] which is a person's belief regarding demands from other people who are considered important to them and are willing to display a certain behavior by the demands, and finally, namely perceived self-control (perceived behavioral control) which is a person's perception of their ability to display a certain behavior [18].

2.2. Turnover Intention

Turnover intention is the tendency of employees to quit their jobs voluntarily because of their desires [19] [20]. Turnover intention is the entry and exit of employees in a company within a certain period/time, which means that there are employees who enter through recruitment and who leave for various reasons that cause changes in the number of employees. [21] says turnover intention is the desire or intention of workers to leave the company or organization and must be replaced immediately. As a step towards realizing that a person's desire to move, namely from one workplace to another, has not been realized. Turnover intention is the desire for an employee to move from one job to another [22]. Five factors cause turnover intention, namely: structural factors, pre-entry factors, environmental factors, trade union factors, and job orientation. Indicators of turnover intention include intention to quit, job search, and thinking of quitting [23] [24].

Results of research conducted by [11][25] state that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. This indicates that higher employee job satisfaction will be able to reduce the level of employee turnover intention. Companies need to increase employee job satisfaction to reduce the level of employee turnover intention within the company.

2.3. Job Stress

According to [26] Work stress is a condition of tension that affects a person's thinking process, emotions, and condition, the result being that excessive stress can threaten a person's ability to deal with the environment and ultimately interfere with carrying out their duties. Job stress is a feeling of pressure experienced by employees when facing work. Work stress is a condition that puts pressure on a person's self and soul beyond the limits of one's abilities [26] or a condition of tension that affects a person's emotions, thought processes, and condition. Factors that influence work stress, namely: work conditions, stress due to roles, interpersonal factors, career development, organizational structure, work home appearance. According to [27][28] describes the indicators of work stress namely: workload, working time, feedback received, responsibilities,

Results of research conducted by [27][26] stated that work stress has a positive and significant influence on employee turnover intention, which shows that the higher the work stress, the greater the increase in turnover intention among employees.

2.4. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a person's feelings towards his work which are produced by his efforts (internal) and supported by things outside himself (external), regarding work conditions, work results, and work itself [10][29]. An employee's positive attitude towards their work arises based on an assessment of the work situation, and this assessment can be carried out on one of their jobs and as a sense of appreciation for achieving one of the important values in work. Job satisfaction is a result of an individual's estimation of a positive and pleasant job or experience. Employees' estimates of their work experience can indicate whether employees feel happy or unhappy with their work. The level of a person's feelings of pleasure as a positive assessment of their work and the workplace environment. Factors that can influence job satisfaction are Fair remuneration or compensation, placement of nurses, workload, work atmosphere and environment, leadership attitude, and job or job attitudes. Indicators of job satisfaction include: work itself, pay, promotion, supervision, and workers [29].

Results of research conducted by [30][31] state that work stress has a negative and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. This indicates that the lower the work stress felt by employees, the higher the job satisfaction felt by employees.

- H1: Work stress has a positive effect on turnover intention.
- H2: Job stress has a negative effect on job satisfaction.
- H3: Job satisfaction has a negative effect on turnover intention.
- H4: Job satisfaction mediates the effect of job stress on turnover intention.

The following is the conceptual framework for this research as follows:

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

3. Materials and Methods

This research was conducted at General Hospital, Gianyar Bali. The population in this study were all nurses in 4 units, namely the Inpatient Unit, Emergency Department, Central Surgery Installation, and Outpatient Unit. The sample in this study was aimed directly at nurses, and a sampling technique was used, namely proportional random sampling so that 100 respondents were obtained for the four units. The object of this research is work stress and job satisfaction turnover intention nurses.

Work stress is defined as an imbalance between the job demands given the abilities possessed and the work environment, which can cause pressure. Indicators of work stress. According to [27][28] namely: workload, working time, feedback received, and responsibilities.

Job satisfaction is a feeling of happiness from a positive assessment of various aspects of work based on evaluation results that meet expectations. Indicators of job satisfaction according to [29] are: work itself, pay, promotion, supervision, and workers.

Turnover intention is an employee's desire or intention to leave the company for various reasons to quit their job to get a better job. Indicator of turnover intention or desire to change nurses. According to [23] [24], namely: intention to quit, job search, thinking of quitting.

Next, the indicators on the variables are reduced to research instruments. For an instrument to obtain reliable results, the instrument must meet the criteria for validity and reliability. The data analysis technique used in this research is quantitative analysis, namely, the structural equation model (Structural Equation Modeling-SEM) variance-based or component-based structural equation model, known as Partial least squares (PLS). The analysis stages using Partial Least Square (PLS) are: Conceptualization of the model, determining the algorithm analysis model, determining the resampling method, drawing path diagrams, and evaluating the model. Mediation testing was carried out by examining the indirect effect of the results of the total indirect effect of the work stress variable on job satisfaction and turnover intention.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Characteristics of respondents

Based on gender, more than half, namely 55 people or 55.0% (percent) of respondents were women, and only 45 people or 45.0% (percent) were men. This indicates that the majority of respondents are female. This shows that women are more dominant as hospital nurses because they are synonymous with femininity and their ability to care for family members. The majority of respondents were aged between 25 and 35 years, namely 31 people or 31.0% (percent), and only 17 people or 17.0% (percent) of respondents were under 25 years old. Based on age, most of the respondents were between 25 and 35 years old. This indicates that nurses are still in the energetic age range, easier to adapt to technology, and have a career path. Based on work experience, the majority of respondents with a work experience of more than 10 years were 38 people or 38.0% (percent), and only 15 people or 15.0% (percent) of respondents had a work period of less than 2 years. Based on the length of service, most of the respondents had work periods of more than 10 years. This shows that nurses have expertise and work experience in their field.

4.2. Inferential Analysis

Inferential analysis in this research uses 2 stages, namely the outer model and the inner model. The measurement model consists of validity tests and reliability tests on indicators of research variables. The validity test and reliability test consist of (a) convergent validity, (b) discriminant validity, dan (c) reliability. The structural model analyzed by (a) Adj. R-Square (R^2), (b) Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q^2), and (c) Goodness of Fit (GoF). Evaluation of the outer model and inner model using SEM-PLS.

4.2.1. Results of the Evaluation of the Measurement Model/Outer Model

Convergent Validity

This evaluation is carried out through examination of the coefficients outer loading each indicator on the latent variable

Table 1 Outer Loading Result

Variable	Indicator	Coefficient Outer Loading	P-Values
Work Stress (X1)	Workload	0.868	0.000
	Working time	0.977	0.000
	Feedback	0.987	0.000
	Responsibility	0.975	0.000
Job Satisfaction (Y1)	The job itself	0.977	0.000
	Income/salary	0.956	0.000
	Promotional opportunities	0.956	0.000
	Supervision	0.967	0.000
	Work colleague	0.961	0.000

Turnover Intention (Y2)	Intention to quit	0.951	0.000
	Job search	0.997	0.000
	Thinking of quit	0.961	0.000

Source: Primary Data Source

Based on Table 1, shows the results of the calculations outer loading of each indicator of work stress, job satisfaction, and turnover intention has a coefficient outer loading greater than 0.50 and p-values namely 0.000 which is significant at an alpha level of 0.05. This proves that the indicators that form the latent variable are valid and significant.

Discriminant Validity

In this analysis measurements discriminant validity is done by knowing the average variance extracted (AVE) value. AVE greater than 0.50. Table 2 shows the results showing that the value AVE all constructs > 0.50, so they meet the valid requirements based on the criteria discriminant validity. Results calculation will AVE ($\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ or square root average variance extracted) in this study are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Discriminant Validity Result

Variable	AVE	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$
Job Stress (X1)	0.869	0.936
Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.938	0.973
Turnover Intention (Y2)	0.942	0.975

Source: Primary Data Source

Composite Reliability and Cronbach’s Alpha

A measurement can be said to be reliable when composite reliability and Cronbach alpha have a value greater than 0.70. Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha a measurements of reliability between indicator blocks in the research model. Table 3 shows that the value of all constructs has shown a value greater than 0.70 so it meets the requirements for reliability based on the criteria composite reliability and Cronbach alpha. The calculation results composite reliability and Cronbach alpha in this research which is processed with the program SmartPLS 3.0, shown in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3 The Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha Result

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha
Job Stress (X1)	0.970	0.943
Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.995	0.982
Turnover Intention (Y2)	0.986	0.964

Source: Primary Data Source

4.2.2. Structural Model Evaluation/Inner Model

R-Square (R²)

Adj.R2 can show the strengths and weaknesses of the influence that the dependent variable has on the independent variable. Adj. R2 can also indicate the strengths and weaknesses of a research model. Table 4.

Table 4 Adj. R-Square (R2) Result

Variable	R-Square Adjusted	Description
----------	-------------------	-------------

Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.878	High
Turnover Intention (Y2)	0.984	High

Source: Primary Data Source

Based on Table 4, the Adj.R2 value for work stress (X1) on job satisfaction (Y1) is 0.878, which means that 87.8% of job satisfaction is influenced by work stress, while the remaining 12.2% is other factors outside the research model. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.878 is classified as a strong model. Adj Value R2 is 0.984, shown by the influence of work stress (X1) and job satisfaction (Y1) on turnover intention (Y2). This means that 98.4% of turnover intention is influenced by work stress (X1) and job satisfaction (Y1). The remaining 1.6% is other factors outside the research model. The Adj.R2 value is 0.984, including the strong category.

Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²)

Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) is a measure of how well the observations made provide results for the research model. MarkQ- Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) ranges from 0 (zero) to 1 (one). The closer to 0 the value Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²), indicates that the research model is getting worse, whereas on the contrary, the further it gets away from 0 (zero) and the closer it gets to the value 1 (one), this means the research model is getting better. The following is the calculation results in Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²):

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - (1 - R^2_1) (1 - R^2_2) \\
 &= 1 - (1 - 0.878) (1 - 0.984) \\
 &= 1 - (0.122) (0.016) \\
 &= 1 - (0.002) \\
 &= 0.998
 \end{aligned}$$

The calculation results Q² amounting to 0.998 (99.8%) can be explained by the relationship between the variables job stress, job satisfaction, and turnover intention while the remaining 0.2% is other factors outside the research model. Refers to the criteria for the strength and weakness of the model based on values Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²), which means this model is quite strong.

Goodness of Fit (GoF)

Goodness of Fit (GoF) is a measurement of the accuracy of the model as a whole because it is considered a single measurement of the measurement outer model and measurement inner model. Measurement value based on Goodness of Fit (GoF) has a value range between 0 (zero) to 1 (one). Mark Goodness of Fit (GoF) The closer it gets to 0 (zero), the less good the model is, conversely, the further it gets away from 0 (zero) and the closer it gets to 1 (one), the better the model. The following is the calculation of Goodness of Fit (GoF), is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{GoF} &= \sqrt{(\text{AVE} \times R^2)} \\
 \text{GoF} &= \sqrt{\left\{ \left[\frac{0.869 + 0.938 + 0.942}{3} \right] \times \left[\frac{0.878 + 0.984}{2} \right] \right\}} \\
 \text{GoF} &= \sqrt{\left[\frac{2.749}{3} \right] \times \left[\frac{1.862}{2} \right]} \\
 \text{GoF} &= \sqrt{0.916 \times 0.931} \\
 \text{GoF} &= \sqrt{0.853} \\
 \text{GoF} &= 0.924
 \end{aligned}$$

The calculation results GoF above, show a value of 0.924, so it refers to the criteria for the strength and weakness of the measurement model through Goodness of Fit (GoF), this model is classified as a strong model.

4.3. Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing was carried out to determine the results of direct and indirect influence tests in this research.

4.3.1. Direct Effect Testing

Hypothesis testing on the direct influence consists of (1) the influence of work stress on turnover intention, (2) the influence of job stress on job satisfaction, and (3) the influence of job satisfaction on turnover intention. The following are the results of the direct influence hypothesis test as follows:

Table 5 Direct Effect of Job Stress, Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

Relationship Between Variables	Coefficient	T	P	Information
	Track	Statistics	Values	
Job Stress (X1) → Turnover intention (Y2)	0.812	10.038	0.000	Significant
Job Stress (X1) → Job Satisfaction (Y1)	-0.942	39.842	0.000	Significant
Job satisfaction (Y1) → Turnover intention (Y2)	-0.191	2.365	0.000	Significant

Source: Primary data processed

Based on Table 5, shows that the test of the path coefficient between work stress and construct turnover intention amounting to 0.812 with a t-statistic coefficient of 10.038 > t-table 1.96 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, indicating that work stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. The results of this test prove hypothesis 1 (H₁), which states that work stress positive influence on turnover intention acceptable.

Testing of the path coefficient between work stress and the construct of job satisfaction is -0.942 with a t-statistic coefficient of 39.842 > t-table 1.96 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, indicating that work stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction. The results of this test prove hypothesis 2 (H₂), which states that work stress negative effect on job satisfaction is acceptable.

Testing of the path coefficient between job satisfaction and constructs turnover intention amounting to -0.191 with a t-statistic coefficient of 2.365 > t-table 1.96 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, indicating that job satisfaction has a negative and significant influence on turnover intention. The results of this test prove hypothesis 3 (H₃), which states that job satisfaction hurts turnover intention.

4.3.2. Indirect Effect Testing

Following are the results of the indirect influence test with job satisfaction mediating the influence of work stress on turnover intention which can be shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Indirect Effect of Job Stress, Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention

Relationship Between Variables	Mediating Variables	Coef. Of Indirect Effect	t-statistics	Description
Job Stress → Turnover Intention	Job Satisfaction	0.188	2.263	Significant

Source: Primary data processed

Based on Table 6, testing of the path coefficient between work stress through job satisfaction towards the construct turnover intention of 0.188 with a t-statistic coefficient of 2.263 > t-table 1.96 and a significance value equal to 0.063 < 0.05. The results of this test prove hypothesis 4 (H₄), Which states that job satisfaction can mediate the relationship between work stress and turnover intention.

The effect of Job Stress on Intention Turnover

Testing on the influence of work stress on turnover intention shows the results that work stress has a positive and significant effect on the turnover intention of nurses. This means, if the work stress of nurses is getting higher, then turnover intention will increase further. Nurses often have to care for several patients at once, which can increase work

pressure. Apart from that, nurses are faced with administrative burdens such as medical records, documentation, and other nursing documentation. Erratic work hours such as night shifts often disrupt nurses' sleep patterns and affect nurses' personal lives, thereby increasing their work stress. The impact of work pressure and work schedules causes nurses to often feel worried and intend to quit their jobs. The results of this study are supported by research [27][26][32] which states that work stress has a positive and significant influence on turnover intention.

The effect of Job Stress on Job Satisfaction

Testing the effect of work stress on job satisfaction shows that work stress has a negative and significant effect on nurses' job satisfaction. This means that if work stress is higher, job satisfaction will decrease. Erratic work schedules make nurses tired so their level of job satisfaction decreases. Apart from that, work also requires a fit body and active movement for several hours. This situation makes nurses feel a high workload and can influence their level of job satisfaction to decrease.

The results of this study are supported by research [30][31] which states that work stress negative and significant effect on job satisfaction.

The effect of job satisfaction on turnover intention

Testing the effect of job satisfaction on turnover intention shows that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention nurses. This means, that if the nurse's job satisfaction is higher, then turnover intention will decrease further. Even though the work they have done is good, they feel there is no opportunity to develop their careers and often do not get the awards or recognition they deserve. This causes the level of satisfaction to decrease, which will result in their desire to leave work becoming higher.

The results of this study are supported by research [11][25] which states that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.

The role of job satisfaction mediates the influence of job stress on turnover intention

Testing the effect of work stress on the turnover intention with job satisfaction as a mediating variable shows that job satisfaction can mediate the effect of job stress on the turnover intention of nurses. This condition indicates that job satisfaction can mediate the relationship between work stress and turnover intention.

High job stress can cause a decrease in job satisfaction because nurses feel dissatisfied with their working conditions, including heavy workloads, lack of support, and uncertainty in work including promotions. In addition, ongoing work stress can increase nurses' desire to change jobs (turnover intention) because they may look for a work environment that is more supportive and less stressful.

The results of this study are supported by research [14][30][33][34] which states that job satisfaction can mediate the influence of work stress on turnover intention.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis, it is proven that if nurses experience work stress it will have an impact on dissatisfaction with work which will then increase their intention to leave the hospital. Nurses who feel the workload is too high and feel that there are no career opportunities for those who have good performance will reduce job satisfaction. Even though nursing is the job they dream of, the high workload and irregular work schedule cause job stress and affect satisfaction and turnover intention.

Changes in nurses' behavior in leaving the hospital occur when their stress levels are high and there is a tendency to decrease job satisfaction. Nurses often think they can advance their careers in hospitals, but in reality, these career opportunities are limited. An important thing is to create a sense of pride in the hospital so that they do not have the desire to look for another place to work. Collaboration between fellow nurses is very important to create a conducive work environment and the work will feel lighter. This research implies that to reduce nurses' intention to move to another workplace, it is important to maintain nurses' job satisfaction and reduce their work stress.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We are very grateful to the respondents who were willing to be involved in this research. Along with all the researchers in this research who have contributed to improving the results of this research.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Funding Statement

This research is funded by Institution of Research and Community Service of Faculty of Economics and Business Universitas Mahasaraswati Denpasar, Bali.

References

- [1] Kurniawaty, K., Ramly, M., & Ramlawati, R. (2019). The effect of work environment, stress, and job satisfaction on employee turnover intention. *Management science letters*, 9(6), 877-886.
- [2] Arshadi, N., & Damiri, H. (2013). The relationship of job stress with turnover intention and job performance: Moderating role of OBSE. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 84, 706-710.
- [3] Bugis, M., ES, D. P., & Saparuddin, S. (2021). The Effect of Job Involvement and Work Stress on Turnover Intention with Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable PT. Perkebunan Minanga Ogan. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, Vol.8, No.9, pp.421-431.
- [4] Uysal, H. T. (2019). The mediation role of toxic leadership in the effect of job stress on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Business*, 24(1), 55-73.
- [5] Mathew, N. A. (2013). Effect of Stress on job satisfaction among nurses in central kerala. *Journal of Business and Management*, 7(2), 47-51.
- [6] Singh, M. M., Amiri, M., & Sabbarwal, S. (2019). Role of job stress on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 6(4), 57-60.
- [7] Alam, A., & Asim, M. (2019). Relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 9(2), 163.
- [8] Devyanti, N. L. P. L., & Satrya, I. G. B. H. (2020). Effect of job satisfaction on turnover intention with organizational commitment as a mediating variable. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(3), 293-298.
- [9] Pratama, E. N., Suwarni, E., & Handayani, M. A. (2022). The effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention with person organization fit as moderator variable. *Aptisi Transactions on Management*, 6(1), 74-82.
- [10] Dewi, I. G. A. M., Rajiani, I., Riana, I. G., Puspitawati, N. M. D., Muafi, M., & Rihayana, I. G. (2023). Women's Risk-Taking Behaviour during COVID-19 Pandemic: Will Work-Family Enrichment and Work Satisfaction Prevent Turnover Intention?. *Administrative Sciences*, 13(3), 67.
- [11] Lai, M. C., & Chen, Y. C. (2012). Self-efficacy, effort, job performance, job satisfaction, and turnover intention: The effect of personal characteristics on organization performance. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 3(4), 387.
- [12] Trivellas, P., Reklitis, P., & Platis, C. (2013). The effect of job related stress on employees' satisfaction: A survey in health care. *Procedia-social and behavioral sciences*, 73, 718-726.
- [13] Junaidi, A., Sasono, E., Wanuri, W., & Emiyati, D. (2020). The effect of overtime, job stress, and workload on turnover intention. *Management Science Letters*, 10(16), 3873-3878.
- [14] Kuo, H. T., Lin, K. C., & Li, I. C. (2014). The mediating effects of job satisfaction on turnover intention for long-term care nurses in T aiwan. *Journal of nursing management*, 22(2), 225-233.

- [15] Ajzen, I. (2011). The theory of planned behaviour: Reactions and reflections. *Psychology & health*, 26(9), 1113-1127.
- [16] Al Ziadat, M. T. (2015). Applications of planned behavior theory (TPB) in Jordanian tourism. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 7(3), 95.
- [17] La Barbera, F., & Ajzen, I. (2020). Control interactions in the theory of planned behavior: Rethinking the role of subjective norm. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 16(3), 401.
- [18] La Barbera, F., & Ajzen, I. (2021). Moderating role of perceived behavioral control in the theory of planned behavior: A preregistered study. *Journal of Theoretical Social Psychology*, 5(1), 35-45.
- [19] Salama, W., Abdou, A. H., Mohamed, S. A. K., & Shehata, H. S. (2022). Impact of work stress and job burnout on turnover intentions among hotel employees. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(15), 9724.
- [20] Lee, Y. L., & Ahn, S. (2015). Impact of job stress on turnover intention among emergency room nurses. *Journal of muscle and joint health*, 22(1), 30-39.
- [21] Wahyono, I., & Riyanto, S. (2020). Effect of organizational commitment, job stress, and job satisfaction on turnover intention. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 8(10), 286-316.
- [22] Ahn, J. Y., & Chaoyu, W. (2019). Job stress and turnover intention revisited: Evidence from Korean firms. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 17(4), 52-61.
- [23] Puspitawati, N. M. D., & Atmaja, N. P. C. D. (2019). The role of organizational commitment mediating organizational climate with turnover intention. *International Journal of Applied Business and International Management (IJABIM)*, 4(3), 23-32.
- [24] Puspitawati, N. M. D., Supartha, I., Dewi, I. G. A. M., & Riana, I. G. (2020). Choosing for leaving a job: what is the most important consideration of married woman?. *Problems and Perspectives Management*, 18(2), 408-417.
- [25] Lambert, E. G., Hogan, N. L., & Barton, S. M. (2001). The impact of job satisfaction on turnover intent: a test of a structural measurement model using a national sample of workers. *The Social Science Journal*, 38(2), 233-250.
- [26] Lim, Y. H., & Cho, Y. C. (2018). Effects of job stress, fatigue, burnout, and job satisfaction on turnover intention among general hospital nurses. *Journal of the Korea academia-industrial cooperation society*, 19(6), 264-274.
- [27] Bhayo, A. R., Shah, N., & Chachar, A. A. (2017). The impact of interpersonal conflict and job stress on employees turnover intention. *International Research Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 45(45), 179-189.
- [28] Javed, M., Khan, M. A., Yasir, M., Aamir, S., & Ahmed, K. (2014). Effect of role conflict, work life balance and job stress on turnover intention: Evidence from Pakistan. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 4(3), 125-133.
- [29] Puspitawati, N. M. D., & Atmaja, N. P. C. D. (2020, October). The Effect of Work-Family Enrichment on Job Satisfaction of Working Mothers. In *Journal of International Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 32-40).
- [30] Sheraz, A., Wajid, M., Sajid, M., Qureshi, W. H., & Rizwan, M. (2014). Antecedents of Job Stress and its impact on employee's Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intentions. *International Journal of Learning & Development*, 4(2), 204-226.
- [31] Jermisittiparsert, K., Petchchedchoo, P., Kumsuprom, S., & Panmanee, P. (2021). The impact of the workload on the job satisfaction: Does the job stress matter?. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 20, 1-13.
- [32] Mosadeghrad, A. M., Ferlie, E., & Rosenberg, D. (2011). A study of relationship between job stress, quality of working life and turnover intention among hospital employees. *Health services management research*, 24(4), 170-181.
- [33] Adebayo, S. O., & Ogunsina, S. O. (2011). Influence of supervisory behaviour and job stress on job satisfaction and turnover intention of police personnel in Ekiti State. *Journal of Management and Strategy*, 2(3), 13.
- [34] Ramlawati, R., Trisnawati, E., Yasin, N., & Kurniawaty, K. (2021). External alternatives, job stress on job satisfaction and employee turnover intention. *Management Science Letters*, 11(2), 511-518.